

BUFFALO FARMING IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

Bangladesh's agricultural economy is heavily focused on agriculture and livestock production, which contributes by creating employment opportunities and making sure people can get enough proteins. Water buffalo are especially important for food security and improving the lives of economically vulnerable populations in rural areas, especially draught purpose and meat production. However, in Bangladesh, water buffaloes have not been fully exploited for milk production. These animals can be found in the coastal areas, river basins, islands and shoal areas (haor in Bengali), where they have adapted very well to the harsh local climates and low-input systems, which means they need minimal investment for feed resources. Despite its potential, water buffalo in Bangladesh has been left behind compared to other livestock like cattle and goats, facing problems like poor breeding programs, limited access to quality feed, lack of modern management practices, and weak veterinary support, which are holding this sector back. There is also a lack of a dedicated buffalo product chain and limited policy focus, constraining its development. However, the government and other organizations are starting to recognize the importance of buffalo farming. They are putting in place things like better breeding programs, targeted policy support, better extension services, and farmer training programs to deal with these issues and get the full potential of buffalo farming.

Keywords: buffalo production, coastal areas, development constraints

Buffalo population and production

Buffalo population is increasing more rapidly in South-Asian countries, than in the rest of the world due to its easy adaptability in coastal areas, disease resilience and utilization of minimal feed sources available¹.

Despite having the same climate conditions, the growth of the buffalo population in Bangladesh is lower than in the neighbouring countries especially India, Pakistan and Nepal which might be due to the absence of high milk-yielding buffalo breed, lack of appropriate breeding and development plans, and less popularity of buffalo products².

According to the Department of Livestock Services (DLS), the total population of buffalo is approximately 1.5

million in Bangladesh. In the Agricultural Census 2019, the buffalo population was 636,926, in which buffalo reported in rural and urban areas were 90% and 10%, respectively. The distribution of buffalo population varies significantly across regions, in coastal regions, such as Bhola, Noakhali, Cox's Bazar, and Barishal districts have the highest concentrations of buffalo³.

These areas provide suitable grazing lands and are less affected by seasonal fodder shortages.

Then riverine areas, including the shoals and floodplains in Sylhet, Mymensingh, and parts of Khulna, also share substantial buffalo populations due to the availability of natural grazing facilities. Other regions,

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▲ **Figure 1.** A Bangladeshi indigenous non-descriptive type of water buffalo in free-range rearing system wallowing in Coastal area. (Source: Udder Health Bangladesh)

such as Rajshahi and Rangpur, have limited buffalo populations, primarily in intensive farming practices. Buffalo population of most of the areas comprise indigenous breeds, which are well-suited to the local climate and management systems but have lower milk yield⁴ (**Figure 1**).

To enhance productivity, some areas adopted crossbred buffaloes, which combine traits of indigenous and high-yielding breeds and are known for comparatively higher milk yield per animal (e.g., Murrah, Nili-Ravi).

Buffalo rearing system

There are five main types of buffalo rearing systems in the country: free-range or bathan, semi-free-range or semi-bathan, intensive, semi-intensive, and household.

► **Figure 2.** Different types of rearing system of buffalo in Bangladesh
A. Extensive or bathan, B. Semi-bathan, C. Intensive, D. Semi-intensive, and E. Household. Photo (Source: UHB and Internet)

(**Figure 2**). The herd size ranges from 1-3 heads for the household system to 50-200 heads for the free-range/bathan and intensive systems.

The Bathan is the saline coastal region where buffaloes are reared in a natural grazing system without a feed supply. In the semi-free-range/semi-bathan system, buffaloes (4-15 head/farm) are kept in the household during the rice growing season and in inland, islands and wetlands during the rest of the year; buffaloes are supplied with roughage and small amounts of concentrates.

In the intensive rearing system, animals are reared in barns and fed in stalls with Napier, German, Jumbo, rice straw and concentrate mixtures. Typically, farms in this system are privately owned, such as Lal Teer Livestock Development Limited and American Dairy Limited, whose primary objective is the improvement of dairy and beef buffaloes through the production and distribution of high-quality semen.

Finally, the household system is characterized by very few head of buffalo reared in the backyard of houses, grazing for 6-7 hours with little or no feed supplementation^{4,5}.

Buffalo product potential and marketing

Buffalo milk is popular for its high nutritional value, with more fat, protein, and total solids compared to cow milk, making it perfect for making products like yogurt, butter, ghee, and cheese.

Fermented milk and yogurt from the Bhola and Noakhali districts are particular favourites. Buffalo milk is most

popular in Mymensingh, Bhola, Noakhali, Natore and Pabna districts because of the high-fat content and chhana (acid curd of milk) that is produced during the processing^{6,7}. Even so, buffalo milk production in Bangladesh is only 0.04% of the global total, which shows that there is a lot of potential to increase the amount of milk produced per animal through better farm management.⁸

In Bangladesh, there are many channels involved in the trade of buffalo milk, including middlemen, milk collection centres, and milk product shops. Buffalo farms are often located far from the places where the milk is processed, and there is not much adherence to hygienic practices. This is because of the poor handling of milk and the long transportation time of the milk without any cooling facilities. As a result, the food safety and quality of the buffalo milk is often compromised⁹. This can lead to contamination by foodborne pathogens, like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and other enteropathogenic organisms¹⁰.

So, it is crucial to improve udder health with proper hygiene practices in all the channels of buffalo milk production to enhance the safety and quality of buffalo milk.

Buffalo meat, also known as "carabeef," is a leaner and healthier alternative to traditional beef, due to the lower fat and cholesterol content.

The carabeef contributes approximately 0.95% to the

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national meat production. It is not as popular in Bangladesh, mainly because people there are not used to eating it, and they do not have much knowledge about how good it is for their health.

However, carabeef is popular in some districts, such as Jamalpur, Rangpur, Chattogram, Cox's Bazar, Comilla and Pabna, where some buffalo meat is produced².

There is no special supply chain for buffalo products like there is for cattle in Bangladesh. This means that there is less choice for consumers, farmers have less profit, and consumers have to pay more for the product. Having a separate supply value chain could help to ensure the authenticity and availability of the buffalo products to the consumers.

Prospects and Constraints of Buffalo Farming

Buffaloes could play a big role in meeting the country's growing demand for protein. As the population grows, there are more and more opportunities to explore high-quality buffalo products such as meat and milk.

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Buffaloes can thrive in many different climates, including flood-prone coastal and riverine areas, making them perfect for using land that has limited agricultural potential. They can also convert low-quality food into valuable products, which makes them important for sustainable farming systems.

Buffalo farming in Bangladesh faces several constraints that retain its growth and production. The main problem is the low genetic potential of indigenous buffalo breeds. There is a lack of organized breeding infrastructure and potential initiatives for genetic improvement. As a result, the production performance of indigenous buffalo in Bangladesh has lower milk and meat yields compared to riverine or other high-yielding breeds.

Another big issue is that there is insufficient availability of feed and fodder, which makes it hard for farmers to provide adequate and quality nutrition year-round. Poor management practices, including lack of technical knowledge among farmers and inadequate housing, further limit productivity. Health-related issues, such

as disease prevalence and limited access to veterinary services, exacerbate the problem.

Additionally, market-related challenges include poorly organized markets for buffalo products and the absence of separate value chains hinder the profitability of the buffalo products.

The fact that there is a lack of technical and logistic support for the buffalo farmers, for example, in terms of programs to help develop the sector, as well as a shortage of research and extension work, and a lack of collaboration between the different stakeholders related to buffalo, is hampering the long-term development of the buffalo sector. Addressing these constraints through strategic interventions is crucial to exploring the potential of buffalo farming in Bangladesh.

Conclusions

Buffalo farming in Bangladesh faces challenges in farming practices, suitable breeds, udder health, production, and reproduction.

Technical interventions and institutional support are needed to overcome these constraints and unlock buffalo farming's potential. Initiatives like selective and crossbreeding through artificial insemination (AI) with quality semen from high-yielding breeds, along with skilled AI technicians, are essential. High bulk milk somatic cell count and bacterial contamination are challenges to udder health and milk quality issues, worsened by poor cleaning, storage, and transportation. Adopting better technologies, disease management, and farmer awareness will help sustain profitable buffalo farming in Bangladesh.

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